
Reactions and Mechanism of Tartrazine and Molybdate Ion in Hydrochloric Acid

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Abstract The reaction and mechanism of tartrazine and molybdate ion in hydrochloric acid has been investigated at a temperature of $T = 30 \pm 1$ °C, $[H^+] = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³ and ionic strength, $\mu = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³. The reaction is first order with respect to both tartrazine and molybdate ion. The rate of reaction was found to decrease with increase in ionic strength concentration and increased with increase in dielectric constant concentration; added cation and anion also increased the rate of reaction. The reaction rate showed increase as the $[H^+]$ increased which obeyed the rate law:

$$\frac{-d}{dt}[TZ^+] = (a + b[H^+])[TZ^+][MoO_4^{-2}]$$

at 30 ± 1 °C, $[H^+] = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, $\mu = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³ (NaCl) and $\lambda_{max} = 560$ nm.

Investigation of spectroscopic test did not indicate the formation of intermediate complex during the course of the reaction as suggested by absence of intercept in Michaelis-Menten plot and lack of shift in λ_{max} . Hence a plausible mechanism in favour of outer-sphere mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords Reaction, Mechanism, Tartrazine, Molybdate ion

Introduction

Tartrazine (TZ⁺), also known as FD and C Yellow no 5, is an artificially produced colouring, water soluble and has a maximum absorbance in an aqueous solution at 560 ± 2 nm [1]. It is a common additive found in foods, beverages, medicines, vitamin supplements, cosmetics, toiletries and other non-food products. It is easy to think of tartrazine as a simple product adding only colour while in reality it is quite different. The primary purpose of tartrazine is to add colour to food, drugs, drinks, creams and lotions, it also introduces the body a range of chemicals. Tartrazine is not just a colour, but is a complex product containing many different chemical compounds by causing adverse reactions, [2] reported on 3 people with a history of rashes that occurred when taking tartrazine coloured drugs. It also causes adverse reactions such as recurrent urticaria, angioedema, and asthma and is frequently implicated in behavioural problems [3]. The most common symptoms linked with tartrazine sensitivity are urticaria and asthma [4].

Molybdate is a compound containing an oxoanion with molybdenum in its highest oxidation state of 6 which is used industrially to catalyze the oxidation of methanol to formaldehyde [5], in industrial water treatment as a corrosion inhibitor and as anode or cathode materials in aqueous capacitor [6-7]. Fertilizers often contain small amounts of molybdate salts [5], also used in the analytical colorimetric testing for the concentration of silica in solution, called the molybdenum blue method [8]. Additionally, it is used in the colorimetric determination of phosphate quantity in association with the dye malachite green.

Applications of tartrazine and molybdate in the industries have mediated the investigation of the reactions and mechanism of tartrazine with molybdate ion. Results obtained on the investigation of this reaction would give an insight into the mechanistic pathway of the dye and the oxoanion.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Analytical grade reagents from BDH Chemical Company England were used without further purification throughout this work. All solutions were prepared with distilled water. HCl and NaCl were used to investigate the effect of hydrogen ion concentration and ionic strength of the reaction medium respectively.

Methods

Stoichiometric Studies

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by spectrophotometric titration, using the mole ratio method. The concentration of the tartrazine = $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was kept constant while that of the molybdate ion was varied at $(0.9 - 3.9) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The reacting mixtures were allowed to stand for 24 hours until the reaction has gone to completion, when the absorbance had attained steady values. The final absorbances were taken and the graph of absorbance against concentration of molybdate was plotted, the stoichiometry was then evaluated from the point of inflection on the graph.

Kinetic Measurements

The rate of depletion in the concentration of the reactant was followed by monitoring the decrease in the absorbance of tartrazine at 560 nm using a UV/Vis spectrum lab 752s. All kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions with the concentration of tartrazine kept constant at $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and that of molybdate ion was maintained at least 9 – folds excess over that of the tartrazine.

Effect of Acid Dependence on Rate of Reaction

The effect of acid dependence on the rate of reaction was studied by keeping the concentration of all other parameters constant while that of the hydrochloric acid were varied between $(0.5 - 3.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Graph of k_2 versus $[\text{H}^+]$ was plotted.

Effect of Change in Ionic Strength on Reaction Rate

The influence of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction was studied by keeping the concentration of all other parameters constant while that of the sodium chloride were varied between $(0.5 - 3.0) \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Graph of $\log k_2$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ was plotted.

Effect of Change in Dielectric Constant on Rate of Reaction

The effect of changes in the dielectric constant of the reaction medium on the reaction rate were investigated by adding acetone and water mixture in a range of (0.2-1.2) % to the reaction mixture, while keeping all other parameters constant.

Effect of Added Cation and Anion on the Rate of Reaction

The effect of added cation and anion on the reaction rate were studied by adding $(0.5 - 3.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of ions (Mn^{2+} and NO_3^-) to the reaction mixture while keeping all other parameters constants.

Test for Intermediate Complex

- Spectroscopic Test: The electronic spectra of the reaction mixtures were run five minutes after the commencement of the reaction. These were compared with the spectra of the dye alone over a wavelength range of 450 – 700 nm.
- Michaelis-Mentens plots of $1/k_1$ versus $1/[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$ were made.

Test for Free Radicals

A solution of 2 ml of acrylamide was added to the partially oxidized reaction mixture containing various concentrations of TZ^+ , MoO_4^{2-} and hydrogen ion, followed by large excess of methanol to initiate free radical polymerization. Acrylamide was also added to each of the reactants separately to serve as control.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry

The result for stoichiometry showed that 1 mole of TZ^+ is consumed by 1 mole of MoO_4^{2-} (Fig.1). This is in good agreement with what was obtained by [9].

Figure 1: Plot of Absorbance versus $[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$ for the determination of the Stoichiometry of the TZ^+ and $[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$.

The overall rate equation is given as:

Kinetics Studies

Plots of $\log(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus time in seconds (where A_t = absorbance at time t and A_∞ = absorbance at infinity) was linear to about 90 % extent of the reaction system indicating a first order dependence of rate on $[\text{TZ}^+]$ (Fig. 2). This is consistent with the results reported by [10] for the reaction of $\text{TZ}^+/\text{BrO}_3^-$. A plot of $\log k_1$ (where k_1 pseudo-first order rate constant) versus $\log [\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$ at constant $[\text{H}^+]$ was also linear with a slope of 0.99 suggesting a first order rate constant with respect to the concentrations of MoO_4^{2-} (Fig. 3). Similar order of one has also been reported for $\text{TZ}^+/\text{BrO}_3^-$ by [10] and [9] for the reaction between ascorbic acid/molybdenum(VI). Second order rate constant, k_2 , were obtained from $k_2 = k_1/[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$ and were found to be fairly constant (Table 1). The second order overall has a rate law written as:

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{TZ}^+] = k_2[\text{TZ}^+][\text{MoO}_4^{2-}] \quad \text{----- 2}$$

where $k_2 = 4.25 \pm 0.01 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Figure 2: Pseudo-first Order Plot for the Reaction of Tartrazine with $\text{MoO}_4^{2-} = (0.9 - 3.9) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. $[\text{TZ}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $T = 30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 560 \text{ nm}$.

Figure 3: Plot of $\log k_1$ versus $[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$ for the Reaction of Tartrazine and Molybdate Ion. $[\text{TZ}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 560 \text{ nm}$.

Table 1: Pseudo-first Order and Second Order Rate Constant for the Reaction of $TZ^+ = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ by MoO_4^{2-} at $30 \pm 1^\circ C$, $[NaCl] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\lambda_{max} = 560 \text{ nm}$.

$10^3 [MoO_4^{2-}] \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$10^3 k_1 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.9	1.0	1.0	3.82	4.24
1.5	1.0	1.0	6.39	4.26
2.1	1.0	1.0	8.92	4.25
2.7	1.0	1.0	11.47	4.25
3.3	1.0	1.0	14.03	4.25
3.9	1.0	1.0	16.65	4.27
1.5	1.0	0.5	5.89	3.92
1.5	1.0	1.0	6.33	4.25
1.5	1.0	1.5	8.23	5.48
1.5	1.0	2.0	8.55	5.70
1.5	1.0	2.5	9.47	6.31
1.5	1.0	3.0	10.27	6.85
1.5	0.5	1.0	6.54	4.36
1.5	1.0	1.0	6.38	4.25
1.5	1.5	1.0	6.17	4.11
1.5	2.0	1.0	5.99	3.99
1.5	2.5	1.0	5.78	3.85
1.5	3.0	1.0	5.57	3.72

Effect of Change in Hydrogen Ion Concentration

The rate constant for the reaction was found to increase with increase in hydrogen ion concentration in the range of $(0.5- 3.0) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 1). Plot of k_H^+ versus $[H^+]$ (Fig. 4) was linear with a slope of 1.21×10^{-4} and an intercept of 3.27 indicating two pathways, acid dependent and acid independent pathways. The acid dependent rate equations for the reaction can be represented by equation 3. This result is consistent with the report given by [11]. However, an inverse first order was reported by [9] for the reaction between ascorbic acid/ MoO_4^{2-} .

$$k_H^+ = (a + b[H^+])[TZ^+][MoO_4^{2-}] \quad \text{----- 3}$$

where $a = 3.27 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $b = 1.21 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$

Figure 4: Plot of k_H^+ versus $[H^+]$ for the Reaction of Tartrazine and Molybdate Ion. $[TZ^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[MoO_4^{2-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 560 \text{ nm}$.

Effect of Ionic Strength

The plot of $\log k_2$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ was made and this gave a straight line with a negative slope of -0.07 (Fig. 5). A negative salt effect was observed in the redox reaction as the rate of reaction was found to decrease with increase in ionic strength of the reaction medium from $0.5 \leq \mu \leq 3.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ indicating that the reaction involved two opposite charges during the course of electron transfer.

Figure 5: Plot of $\log k_2$ versus $\sqrt{\mu}$ for the Reaction of Tartrazine and Molybdate Ion at $[TZ^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[MoO_4^{2-}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 560 \text{ nm}$.

Effect of Added Cation and Anion

Manganese ion (Mn^{2+}) and NO_3^- increased the rate of reaction as the concentrations of the ions increased (Table 2).

Test for Presence of Free Radicals

Addition of acrylamide solution (2 ml) to the partially reacted mixture did not indicate formation gel even in the presence of excess methanol.

Spectroscopic Analysis

The plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[MoO_4^{2-}]$ gave no intercept indicating absence of a precursor complex formation prior to electron transfer (Fig. 6).

Table 2: Effect of Added Cation and Anion

$[TZ^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[MoO_4^{2-}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 560 \text{ nm}$

Ions	$10^3 [Ion] \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$10^3 k_1 s^{-1}$	$k_2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Mn^{2+}	0.5	5.97	3.98
	1.0	6.39	4.26
	1.5	6.82	4.55
	2.0	7.24	4.83
	2.5	7.69	5.13
	3.0	8.12	5.42
NO_3^-	0.5	6.11	4.07
	1.0	6.38	4.25
	1.5	6.85	4.57
	2.0	7.32	4.88
	2.5	7.84	5.23
	3.0	8.32	5.55

Figure 6: Graph of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$ for the Reaction of Tartrazine and Molybdate Ion at $[\text{TZ}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 560 \text{ nm}$.

Reaction Mechanism

From equation 4

$$\text{HMoO}_4^- = K_1[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}][\text{H}^+] \quad \text{---- 7}$$

Equations 5 and 6 are the rate determining steps, therefore:

$$\text{Rate} = k_2[\text{TZ}^+][\text{HMoO}_4^-] + k_3[\text{TZ}^+][\text{MoO}_4^{2-}] \quad \text{---- 8}$$

Substituting equation 7 into 8

$$\text{Rate} = k_2K_1[\text{TZ}^+][\text{MoO}_4^{2-}][\text{H}^+] + k_3[\text{TZ}^+][\text{MoO}_4^{2-}] \quad \text{---- 9}$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_3 + k_2K_1[\text{TZ}^+][\text{MoO}_4^{2-}][\text{H}^+] \quad \text{---- 10}$$

Equation 10 is similar to equation 3

$$\text{where } k_3 = 'a' = 3.27 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ and } k_2K_1 = 'b' = b = 1.21 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

The following points were considered in order to assign a plausible mechanism for the reaction:

The Michaelis-Menten plot of $1/k_1$ versus $1/[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$ was linear without an intercept indicating the absence of intermediate complex formation. This suggests an outer-sphere mechanism [12].

Absence of spectrophotometric evidence of intermediate complex formation suggests that an intermediate complex was probably not formed prior to electron transfer and that the redox reaction most probably occurs by outer-sphere mechanism.

It is therefore evident from the above that the reaction of tartrazine with molybdate ion most probably occurred by the outer-sphere mechanism.

Conclusion

From the results obtained, it was observed that the reduction is first order in both $[\text{TZ}^+]$ and $[\text{MoO}_4^{2-}]$. The rate of reaction was found to decrease with increase in ionic strength concentration and added Cation and anion increased

the rate of reaction. The reaction rate showed increase as the $[H^+]$ increased. Investigation of spectroscopic test did not indicate the formation of intermediate complex during the course of the reaction as suggested by absence of intercept in Michaelis- Menten plot and lack of shift in λ_{max} . Plausible mechanism in favour of outer-sphere mechanism has been proposed.

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